

Halogenation. Part XV. Chlorination and Bromination of Cumene and *p*-Cymene.

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p-Chloro- and *p*-bromocumenes as well as 2-chloro-*p*-cymene and 2:5-dichloro-*p*-cymene have been obtained by the action of the halogens on the hydrocarbons in presence of iodine or aluminium chloride (Genvesse, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1893, iii, 9, 223; Jacobson, *Ber.*, 1879, 12, 430; Gerichten, *Ber.*, 1877, 10, 1249; Junger and Klages, *Ber.*, 1896, 29, 314). Among the side-chain compounds, 1'-bromocumene has been obtained by direct bromination (Wheeler and Johnson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, 24, 680) while 1'-chloro-, 1':2'-dibromo- and 1':2'-dichlorocumenes have been obtained by indirect methods only, whereas chlorination of *p*-cymene even under conditions most favourable for side-chain substitution, has been reported to result mostly in nuclear substitution, giving very poor yields of side-chain substituted derivatives (Quist, *Forth III nord, Kemistmotet*, 1928, 194). The present work was undertaken to investigate in full the action of chlorine and bromine on cumene and *p*-cymene in sunlight as well as in presence of halogen carriers such as aluminium chloride, ferric chloride, palladium chloride, lithium bromide, vanadium trioxide, iron, aluminium, tungsten, selenium, tellurium, thallium, sulphur, antimony, pyridine, etc. Working in sunlight 1':2'-dichloro-, 1'-bromo- and 1':2'-dibromocumenes have been prepared. In diffused daylight chloro- and bromocumenes and the following new di- and mixed halogen derivatives have been obtained:—(i) *p*-chloro-1'-chlorocumene, (ii) *p*-bromo-1'-bromocumene and (iii) *p*-chloro-1'-bromocumene. By brominating 2-chloro-*p*-cymene a new chloro-bromo derivative, 2-chloro-5-bromo-*p*-cymene, has been obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL.

p-Chloro-1'-chlorocumene.—Through cumene (10 c. c.) containing 1 c. c. of a 15% solution of iodine in acetic acid pure chlorine gas was passed for about 6 hours in diffused sunlight. The solid product was removed by filtration, dried, extracted with benzene, washed free of chlorine and crystallised, m. p. 180°; yield 1.1 g. (Found: Cl, 36.97 C₉H₁₀Cl₂ requires Cl, 37.23 per cent). The liquid portion was washed free of chlorine, dried and distilled under reduced pressure and was found to be 4-chlorocumene (3 c. c., b. p. 122-124°/12 mm.). The solid product gave on oxidation, *p*-chlorobenzoic acid. Hence the second chlorine atom must be in the side-chain. Since substitution takes place with the elimination of hydrogen attached to the carbon

nearest to the nucleus (Schramm), the compound in question must be *p*-chloro-1'-chlorocumene.

p-Bromo-1'-bromocumene.—(i) *From cumene*. To cumene (5 c. c.) and iodine solution (1 c. c.), bromine (4 c. c.) was added with constant shaking and allowed to stand for 8 hours in diffused sunlight. The solid product was filtered, dried, extracted with benzene and crystallised as needles (1.2 g.), m. p. 226°. (Found: Br., 57.3. $C_9H_{10}Br_2$ requires Br, 57.6 per cent). The liquid portion on washing, drying and distillation gave *p*-bromocumene (3.5 c.c.)

(ii) *From p-bromocumene*.—The previous experiment was repeated with *p*-bromocumene (5 c. c.), yield 1.1 g.

(iii) *From 1'-bromocumene*.—1'-Bromocumene on similar treatment with bromine gave 0.7 g. of the compound.

Since the same compound is obtained from *p*-bromocumene as well as from 1'-bromocumene this new compound is *p*-bromo-1'-bromocumene.

p-Chloro-1'-bromocumene.—(i) *From p-chlorocumene*.—*p*-Chlorocumene (5 c. c.) and iodine solution (1 c. c.) were treated for about 8 hours with bromine (2 c. c.) in diffused sunlight. The product was worked up as before, m.p. 207°, yield 1.4 g. (Found: Total halogen, 49.5. $C_9H_{10}ClBr$ requires total halogen, 49.5 per cent).

(ii) *From 1'-bromocumene*.—Through 1'-bromocumene (10 c.c.) and iodine solution (1 c.c.) in a flask, chlorine was passed in diffused sunlight for 3 hours. The solid was filtered and crystallised from absolute alcohol as needles, yield 2.3 g.

p-Chlorocumene on bromination and 1'-bromocumene on chlorination gave the same chlorobromo derivative. Hence the new compound is *p*-chloro-1'-bromocumene.

2-Chloro-5-bromo-*p*-cymene.—2-Chloro-*p*-cymene (5 c.c.), and powdered iron (1 g.) were taken in a flask and bromine (2 c.c.) was added slowly with shaking at the ordinary temperature. After 7 hours the contents were extracted with benzene, washed free of bromine in the usual way, dried and distilled. The fraction distilling at 247° (3.1 c.c.) was collected. (Found: Total halogen, 45.8. $C_{10}H_{12}ClBr$ requires total halogen, 46.6 per cent). It is a heavy oily liquid almost colourless when pure, undergoing slight decomposition on standing and insoluble in water. When a vigorous current of chlorine was passed into the chloro-bromo compound, the bromine was displaced by chlorine and 2:5-dichloro-*p*-cymene was formed. Hence the compound must be 2-chloro-5-bromo-*p*-cymene.

The results obtained with different compounds under varying conditions are summarised below in a tabular form.

Substance.	Halogen.	Halogenating agent.	Product and yield.
Cumene (10 c.c.)	Cl passed for 3 hours in diffused sunlight.		4-Chlorocumene (b.p. 122-124° / 12 mm.), 6.0 g.
	Cl passed for 3 hours in sunlight.		1':2'-Dichlorocumene (b.p. 118°/12 mm.), 3.7 g.
	Br (4 c.c.) in diffused sunlight and allowed to stand for 12 hours.	AlBr ₃ (1 g.)	4-Bromocumene (b.p. 220°), 11.7 g.
	Do	Iodine solution (1 c.c.)	4-Bromocumene, 12.1 g.
	Do	Thalium nitrate (1 g.)	4-Bromocumene, 10.8 g.
	Br (4 c.c.) in sunlight and allowed to stand for 5 hours in the sun.		1-Bromocumene (b.p. 188-189°) 4-Bromocumene (b.p. 225°), 1.4 g.
	Br (8 c.c.) in sunlight and allowed to stand for 5 hours in the sun.		1'-Bromocumene (b.p. 188-189°), 2.6 g. 1':2'-Dibromocumene (b.p. 140°/115 mm.), 8.7 g. 4-Bromocumene, traces.
<i>p</i> -Cymene (20 c.c.)	Cl passed in diffused sunlight for 4 hours.	Iron (2 g.)	2-Chloro- <i>p</i> -cymene (b.p. 216°), 10.1 g. 2:5-Dichloro- <i>p</i> -cymene (b.p. 244°), 1.6 g.
<i>p</i> -Cymene (10 c.c.)	Cl passed in diffused sunlight for 4 hours.	Iodine solution (1.5 c.c.)	2-Chloro- <i>p</i> -cymene (b.p. 216°), 6.1 g. 2:5-Dichloro- <i>p</i> -cymene (b.p. 244°), 1.6 g.
	„	FeCl ₃ (1.5 g.)	2-Chloro- <i>p</i> -cymene (b.p. 216°), 4.8 g. 2:5-Dichloro- <i>p</i> -cymene (b.p. 244°), traces.
	„	Uranium oxide (1.5 g.)	2-Chloro- <i>p</i> -cymene (b.p. 216°), 5.9 g. 2:5-Dichloro- <i>p</i> -cymene (b.p. 244°), traces.
	„	„	2-Chloro- <i>p</i> -cymene (b.p. 216°), 5 g. 1'-Chloro- <i>p</i> -cymene (b.p. 226-229°), 8.6 g.
<i>p</i> -Cymene (20 c.c.)	Cl passed in sunlight for 7 hours.		2-Chloro- <i>p</i> -cymene (b.p. 216°), 5 g. 1'-Chloro- <i>p</i> -cymene (b.p. 226-229°), 8.6 g.